

A Legal Analysis of Indecent Representation of Women In Media

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Abstract

The development of any civilization can be assumed from the status of its women. It has been seen that the special role of women as progenitor's has led the other half of the population to consider them as vulnerable, weak and meant to be kept inside the four walls of the house. From the earliest times of the human race, the situation of women has not been the same, rather it has been a gradual process of deterioration. To address the deplorable state of women, a movement called feminism developed. It gave recognition to the rights of women and is still fighting to give them equal and dignified presence. This whole movement has been in a gradual process of development. Within this a debate arose with regard to the objectification of women. In India, the question across sexuality and objectification has gone through a long journey and debate. The ever-expansive media industry and the various rules to regulate its content have ignited the questions more forcefully. Freedom of speech and expression is ensured to Indian media but subject to reasonable restrictions, inter alia, public order, decency or morality. This study focused on "women" with consideration of "gender". "Media" under this work includes the way of public communication reaching to a larger, scattered and heterogeneous audience with special emphasis on visual media and focus on movies and advertisements. The objectives of this research was to study objectification of women in media and its impact; to examine the legal regulations for media content in India and lacunas to prevent objectification of women in media.

Key words: Indecent Representation; Objectification; Media.

Introduction

The question around sexuality has always triggered debate in India. From time to time due to the expansive media industry in India, laws have been legislated to regulate content through broadcasting rules and most importantly through the Indecent Representation of Women (Prohibition) Act, 1986.¹ Although freedom of speech and expression provided under Article 19(1)(a) of the Constitution of India gives every freedom to the media to advertise and make cinematographic films subject to reasonable restrictions, inter alia, public order, decency or morality. Feminism talks about equality but is opposed to the objectification of women, while the law also wants to restrict indecency, obscenity without curbing the freedom of expression. All these complexities mostly cater to obscenity, profanity, vulgarity, and indecency but overlook objectification of women which finds no specific definition in any statute although mentioned in various philosophical and feminist writings.

Objectification of Women in India

The existence known as "woman" is not exactly born, rather she is shaped and manufactured by the dictums of society and civilization. She is an outlet for all of mankind's worst fetishes and depravities. She is not meant to have any rights but to be a mere plaything for mankind - a mere sex toy to be enjoyed at will. She is a silent spectator, the object, and never the subject of any work. To sing, to dance,

to dress and roll the eyes – that is her creed. She is meant to look good and satisfy the male gaze. If her controllers demand sensuality she must bare herself; if they demand her embarrassment, she must act coy; if they demand her to abstain from the public sphere, she must remain behind veils. This is what patriarchy wants of her, and this is what media propagates.² Media, which is but a mere tool in the hands of patriarchy, strengthens this notion in the general mind and gives her a sensualized or idealized image as and when demanded by patriarchy.

The Mass Media

Firstly ‘mass communication’ which is a very frequently used term is different from ‘media’. Mass communication is the information transmitted to large segments of the population. While the transmission of information or mass communication may happen through many different kinds of media (plural form of medium), which is the means of transmission and it can be print, digital, or electronic. Mass media specifically refers to a means of communication that is designed to reach a larger audience. Mass media platforms are commonly considered to include radio, newspaper, magazines, books, video games, and internet media such as blogs, podcasts, and video sharing.³ The media and film industry has found ways to upgrade themselves with the technology that draws customers and keeps them solvent.

Projection of Women in Media as Object

Objectification is the process through which complex and often abstract concepts are gradually transformed through social exchange into concrete visual images.⁴ Immanuel Kant believes that the viewing and interpretation of a person as an object which only exists for his or her sexual pleasure is called objectification.⁵

It is the process of expressing a person as an object to be owned or consumed, rather than an individual entity. Examples include the use of women’s bodies and body parts to sell products; or images that only show parts of women’s bodies; or depictions of women as inanimate objects for consumption.⁶

Literature Review

Broadly Media can be designated as any channel of communication.⁷ It includes digital data, art, craft, and various other forms of communication.⁸ Media is a substantial game-changer with the power of supplying food for updates to mental models.⁹ It can generate behavioral change.¹⁰ In recent years it has been observed that the media has appeared as the major exploiter of women. Media alienates women from bodies by a gender system and arduous appearance maintenance, modification, self-conscious posture, gesture, and clothing which invites the male gaze.¹¹ The “objectification” or “sexual objectification” of women is viewing and treating a person as an object. This treatment is because women’s bodies are culturally constructed. **Barbara L. Frederickson** and **Tomi-Ann Roberts** observe that “bodies exist within social and cultural contexts, and hence are also constructed through socio-cultural practices and discourses.”¹² **Margaret Jane Radin** writes “we are, I think, both pretty well proof against commodification (objectification) and pretty well commodified (objectified).”¹³ **Catharine A. MacKinnon** opines that women “exist to the end of male pleasure” while **Andrea Dworkin** understands similarly that a man uses the whole object world as he is the “centre of a chattel-oriented sensibility”¹⁴ **Jochen Peter** and **Patti M. Valkenburg** had described that the increased sexual content in the media and the sexualized portrayal of women in advertisements went up significantly between 1983 and 2003.¹⁵ In advertisements, women scantily clad are used for selling the product in every possible media and film also shows the same trend.¹⁶

Importance of the Study

Gender discrepancy is a major problem that the UN wants to fight, and it is considered one of the sustainable development goals (SDGs). But in the achievement of this goal, various obstacles are there and the depiction of women in media is one of the major obstacles as identified by various international bodies. The portrayal can either be positive or negative through stereotypical depiction and the latter also includes objectification of women which will be the major concern of study in this research.

Thus, this study will help to provide to the issue of gender inequality promoted by the media industry and how the projection of women as an object matters too seriously when gender issues come into

question. This study will help to find out the deep-rooted problem of objectification of women which is not much discussed in the legal parlance. Objectification of women has been a bone of contention for feminists and it has been separately studied in the academic, philosophical, and psychological arena. However, this research does a cross-sectional study on this issue in concern with specific emphasis on India and thus is very significant.

Scope

The distinction between sex and gender lies in the person's biological anatomy for the former and consideration of social and cultural roles for the latter. The meaning of "women" has been taken into consideration through the lens of "gender" in this study. "Media" under this work includes ways of public communication reaching a large, scattered, heterogeneous audience. It implies communication through certain channels or mechanism which may be mediated or unmediated, for example, TV, film, radio, face-to-face, internet, books, art, music, newspapers, magazines, podcasts, blogs, and any other means of communication mechanism of like nature. The special emphasis of this study has been on visual media with a focus largely on movies and advertisements. Synonymous terms of "representation" have been used throughout the work such as depiction and projection. "Content" of representation for the work includes words, images, sounds, symbols, etc. In this study, the "indecent representation of women" incorporates the objectification of women. The depiction of women in media especially as an object will be the main concern of this study.

Research Methodology

This research is done through the doctrinal methodology of research. The identificatory model of research has been accepted in this study as it tries to ascertain as to the beneficiaries for whom the legal provisions are existing. This model helps to ascertain whether the parties intended to be benefited are being benefited or not. The interpretative model has also been taken into consideration while completing the research work as case-law, statutes, rules, regulations and other legal sources are tools of this undertaken research.

Media Regulation

Media Theories Structuring Media Regulation It is really relevant to get a glimpse of media theories to understand the idea of media regulation. These theories essentially relate to the dynamic social-political and philosophical concepts that structure media-society relationships. These are discussed briefly as follows: The normative theory that speaks about what media should do in society rather than what they actually do. In the book *Four Theories of the Press* (1956) it is well expressed through the following line the press takes on the form and colour of social and political structures'.¹⁷ In their opinion, the press and other media should represent the "core values and expectations held by society." While the western liberal tradition involves topics such as freedom, social solidarity and cohesion, cultural diversity, equality before the law, active commitment, and social responsibility. Similarly, different cultures have different priorities and principles.¹⁸ Because of changes and emergence of new media reforms, this theory is in a considerable state of uncertainty.

Leading Cases on Indecent Representation of Women

I. A.K. Gopalan v. State of Madras¹⁹

In this case it was held that "There can never be absolute and unrestricted freedom that is completely devoid of restrictions because that would cause chaos. The possession and enjoyment of all rights are subject to any reasonable restrictions that the nation's governing body may determine necessary for the public's safety, health, peace, and morals. On the other hand, social control that is in place for the public good needs to be limited lest it be abused to the damage of individual rights and liberties. In some circumstances, constraints must be placed on the free enjoyment of individual rights to protect the interests of society. On the other hand, society must empower itself with some powers in order to safeguard these liberties in and of themselves. Therefore, the Constitution seeks to find a balance between personal freedom and societal control by stating the rights of the people." The Indian Constitution's Article 19 lists a number of personal

liberties, along with the restrictions that must be adhered to. These limitations are placed on them only to preserve public morals and the general good of society.

II. **Ranjit D. Udeshi v. State of Maharashtra**²⁰

In this landmark case, established the "test of obscenity," in which a bookshop was charged under the IPC for selling an unedited and expurgated copy of "Lady Chatterley's Lovers." In order to maintain "public decency and morality" and "freedom of speech and expression," a delicate balance must be struck; but, when the latter is materially violated, the latter must fall. According to the Indian Penal Code, Section 292, it was decided that "in appraising a work, stress should not be focused upon a word here and a word there, or a passage here and a passage there." He was found guilty under this provision. Although the entire piece must be taken into consideration, the obscenity must also be looked at separately to determine whether it is as vile and deliberate as to deprave and corrupt individuals whose brains are susceptible to such effects. In this context, it's important to keep in mind the interests of modern society, in particular how the contested book has affected it.

III. **Chandra Raja Kumari v. Police Commissioner, Hyderabad**²¹

In this case it was held that holding a beauty contest is disrespectful to women's dignity and decency and breaches Article 21 of the Constitution because the right to life also encompasses the right to live in dignity or decency. Human dignity is acknowledged by both the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights.

IV. **Aveek Sarkar v. State of West Bengal**²²

In this case the Indecent Representation of Women (Prohibition) Act of 1986 and the Indian Penal Code of 1860 were both violated in a photo of tennis player Boris Becker and his dark-skinned fiancée Barbara Feltus standing nude. According to the court, which placed emphasis on the Community Standards test, "The message the photograph tries to portray is that skin color is not particularly important and that love triumphs over color." The picture depicts a white man falling in love with a black woman and getting married as a result. As a result, we should evaluate the images and the narrative in light of the message they are attempting to convey, which is to eradicate racism and prejudice as negative social forces and to promote romantic relationships and marriages between white men and black women. We are not yet prepared to make the case that the picture or the piece of writing, which Sports World and the Anandabazar Patrika both used, is objectionable enough to call for legal action under Section 292 of the IPC or Section 4 of the Indecent Representation of Women (Prohibition) Act of 1986.

V. **Chandrakant Kalyandas Kakodar v. State of Maharashtra**²³

In this case it was decided that there were no set criteria for defining obscenity and that each country would define obscenity differently depending on the moral norms of the time.

VI. **Maneka Gandhi v. Union of India**²⁴

In this case it was held that the right to life extends beyond simple physical survival and includes the ability to live in dignity.

VII. **Francis Coralie v. Union of Territory of Delhi**²⁵

In this case of it was held that the term "human dignity" refers to more than just physical survival and encompasses "the right to live with human dignity" for women as well as preservation of all faculties and limbs used to enjoy life or connect with the outside world. Therefore, women have access to all human rights. Women have right to live a dignified life.

VIII. **Ajay Goswami v. Union of India**²⁶

In this case the Indecent Representation of Women Act, the IPC, and other statutes were used to dispute the publication of pornographic material in newspapers. The press council act of 1978 and section 292 of the IPC are two pieces of regulating legislation that the court noted as being in place to prevent such obscene publishing. The court ruled that the content should be

independently assessed to determine if it is profoundly depraved and corrupt for a publication to be considered obscene.

Conclusion

The society of today desires to uphold a certain standard of morality and decency. The freedom of expression of Media and each individual and the responsibility of the state to uphold public morals should coexist in harmony. The media is a replication of society, and media stories replicate what is going on in society. It can be appealed that people tolerate and ignore vulgarly presenting women in advertising, whether they appear on hoardings or in other forms of media. Officers have a responsibility to apply the Indecent Representation of Women (Prohibition) Act, 1986, which can be used to get posters featuring obscene depictions of women taken down. A writ of mandamus may be used in following situations.

The Supreme Court has acknowledged in a number of judgments that advertising were inherently business communication and hence qualified for protection under Art. 19(1). (a). Because of the constraints, which include, among other things, considerations of morality and decency, it must be kept in mind that this is not a general protection. It was further ruled that while both modelling agencies and advertising models have a right to a living and a profession, it is on to so-called social workers, activists, lawyers, and media professionals to educate society as a whole regarding the repercussions of immoral behaviour on the law.

The IT revolution has further expanded the media's significance. Media has enormous power to affect the general public. The media now play a significant influence in forming contemporary society. Mass media, which offers information and instruction in addition to enjoyable entertainment, is crucial in a nation like India for raising public awareness of national policies and programs. Everybody and every place have their own standards of decency. The standards of propriety and other things continue to change as society advances and people's lifestyles change. Women should be projected in a responsible and empowered way, rather than as sex objects or glam dolls, in order to have the greatest impact on society and to transform people's attitudes and behaviors about women.

The Preamble of the Indian Constitution grants the State the power to enact measures of positive discrimination in women's favor in addition to guaranteeing women's equality. India has also enacted various laws to secure equal rights of women.

Without a doubt, the Act created women's indecent portrayal, although this list is not all inclusive. It is open to interpretation by the courts in whatever way they see fit. It is a successful law that protects the honor and reputation of women, but how well it is applied will determine how effective it is. It is our responsibility to be aware of the actions that undermine Indian society and culture at its very core. The media is a tool for bringing gender-related issues to the attention of decision makers, including the gender wage gap, infant and maternal mortality, crime against women, gender-based violence, acid attacks, dowry-related issues, girl child issues, issues with women's labor, and the effects of poverty on women and their families.

In order to promote respect and dignity for women and avoid unfavorable portrayals of them, the media should facilitate acceptable and dignified representation of women. The media industry needs to be made more aware of gender issues, and a system of prizes for portraying women well may be devised. Hence, strict regulations are needed to control the indecency.

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